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PRINCIPALS' OPENNESS AND AGREEABLENESS AS CORRELATE OF THEIR ADMINISTRATIVE EFFECTIVENESS IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ANAMBRA STATE

Mokwe, Nwamaka Florence

Prof. Emenike Obi

Department of Educational Management and Policy,
Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State

Corresponding author: nf.mokwe@unizik.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

This study investigated principals' openness and agreeableness as correlate of their administrative effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State. Two research questions guided the study and two hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. A correlational survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consisted all the 263 principals in the six education zones of Anambra State. All the principals were used for the study. Two sets of researchers'-developed instrument titled "Principals' Openness and Agreeableness Questionnaire" (POAQ) and "Principals' Administrative Effectiveness Questionnaire" (PAEQ) were used for data collection. The instruments were validated by three experts and subjected to internal consistency test using Cronbach's Alpha method which yielded 0.81 for POAQ and 0.89 for PAEQ. Pearson' Product Moment Correlation Co-efficient was used to analyze data for the study. The findings of the study indicated that there is a strong positive relationship between principals' openness and agreeableness and their administrative effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State. Based on the findings it was recommended among others that there is need for Post Primary School Service Commission to determine the personality traits of would be principals before their appointment to ensure they possess requisite traits to manage the affairs of the schools for effectiveness.

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Introduction

Education is seen as a crucial tool for national and personal development in every country. This is because the level of a nation's literacy determines her extent of development. Education transforms lives and is a human right for all throughout life (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, (UNESCO), 2021). A well administered education would equip individuals with the capacity to understand and adapt to new problems and changing situations, awaken intellectual curiosity, encourage their spirit of inquiry and make them inventive, self-reliant and resourceful (Federal Republic of Nigeria, (FRN), 2014).

The education system in Nigeria is delineated into different levels, basic education, post basic education and tertiary education. The post basic education (secondary education) has the broad goals of preparing individuals for useful living in the society and for higher education. This has made it imperative that it should, among others, supply trained manpower in the applied science, technology and commerce at sub-professional levels; inspire its students with the desire for self-improvement and achievement of excellence; raise a generation of people who can think for themselves, respect the views and feelings of others and respect the dignity of labour (FRN, 2014). In order to achieve these lofty goals, effective leadership from the principal is crucial.

Leadership effectiveness is the ability to influence individual and collective efforts of others to get work done for the attainment of a common objective. According to Ibukun, Oyewole and Abe (2011), leadership effectiveness refers to the ability of the school principal to effectively carry out administrative tasks related to instructional programming, staff personnel administration, student personnel administration, financial and physical resources, and school community relations toward achieving the school goals and objectives.

According to Alimi, Alabi and Ehinola (2011) principals' leadership effectiveness is the overall school effectiveness in relation to the attainment of both normative and summative values in students. The leadership effectiveness of principals is evident when they influence members of staff to get work done through disseminating timely information to staff, strict on professional ethics in school, regular supervision of teachers, providing rewards commensurate to staff performance, initiating school development programme and utilization of the limited funds for the provision of school infrastructures to attainment academic excellence of students. The leadership effectiveness of principals is a function of their behaviour which reflects their personality trait. Danlami and Auwalu (2020) stressed that principals like every other individual have different interests, abilities and special personality characteristics. Every leader has personality traits that influence his behaviour and administrative style.

A personality trait is the distinctive pattern of behaviour, thought and emotion of an individual. Ashok and Ritu (2016) defined personality traits as a complex of qualities and characteristics or the pattern of thought, emotion, and behaviour of one people that is stable across time. Personality trait is constant behaviour and attitude that distinguish a person from the other. Gana, Oluwafeyisayomi and Idowu (2020) defined personality traits as consistent differences between the behaviours and characteristics of two or more people. The personality traits that have received much attention in literature is the "Big Five" model by McCrae and Costa (2006) which consists of five aspects of personality, namely: extraversion, neuroticism, openness to experience, agreeableness and conscientiousness.

An openness personality trait is a unique feature of being curious, creative and sensitive to new ideas and development. Openness can best be described as a person's willingness to try new things and be open to new experiences (Gadisa, 2020). The principals of secondary schools who possess openness traits exhibit behaviour beyond the status quo by accepting innovative ways of performing a task. Openness is a general appreciation for art, emotion, adventure, unusual ideas, imagination curiosity and variety of experience. Principals with the openness trait are broad-minded, polite and helpful to teachers. They are generally very active, have a tremendous inclination towards creativity and aesthetics and listen to their hearts (Adeniyi & Anuodo, 2018). Such principals are generally open to new learning, skill sets and experiences. Principals who score high on openness are quite broadminded and modern in their outlook as compared to those who score low on the same parameter. Such principals are conservative, reluctant to changes and have a traditional approach in life.

Agreeableness is a personality trait of being cooperative, caring and courteous. According to Gadisa (2020), agreeableness refers to the basic emotional style of a person, who may be easygoing, friendly and pleasant (at the high end of the scale) or grumpy, crabby and hard to get along with (at the low end). Ajayi, Waliu, Adewale, Opeyemi and Olowoporoku (2017) noted that agreeableness is a tendency to be compassionate and cooperative rather than suspicious and antagonist towards others. Animba (2020) pointed out that people with the high agreeable trait are helpful, trusting, sympathetic and empathetic. They are cooperative which makes them easily get along with members of staff. Principals who score high on agreeableness are ready to help their staff and usually smile whenever a problem arises (Adeniyi & Anuodo, 2018). Conversely, principals who score low on agreeableness find it difficult to adjust for the sake of others and are unfriendly.

There are reports that some principals in secondary schools in Anambra State seem uncooperative and unhelpful to their teachers probably due to their personality traits. Some of them are resistant to change probably due to their inherent absence of openness trait. In some cases, they tend to be arrogant and deliberately disengage themselves from associating with teachers. These situations create confusion and chaos in the school and appear to undermine principals' leadership effectiveness in the school.

Statement of the Problem

Ideally, effective administration manifests in the ability of principals to be passionate about learning and having a clear vision on how schools can promote high levels of achievement for all students; equitably delegate routines and duties to teachers or subordinates to allow them have control over their job; make sure there is direction in work so as not to facilitate role conflict; to timely receive rewards from government and school management board. But this ideal situation seems far from been achieved by principals in secondary schools in Anambra State because most schools still witness administrative crises.

Observable situation revealed that the selection of principals which is based on teaching experience and not on administrative qualification has been alleged to contribute to the inefficiency and lapses found in secondary schools. Many principals as a result seem inadequately prepared for the psychological and emotional realities of their job hence, a good number of them often times are unable to deal with the situation they find themselves. A lot of stressors take their toll them in their bid to carry out their administrative functions and attain educational goals. This is manifested in the frictions and tensions that often exist between principals and staff which undermine healthy interpersonal relationship and the realization of effective school administration. This study therefore

determined principals' openness and agreeableness as correlate of their administrative effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between principals' openness and their administrative effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State?
2. What is the relationship between principals' agreeableness and their administrative effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. There is no significant relationship between principals' openness and their administrative effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. There is no significant relationship between principals' agreeableness and their administrative effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Methods

A correlational survey research design was adopted for the study which was carried out in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria. Two research questions guided the study and two hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance. All the 263 principals in Anambra State were used for the study. Two researchers' developed instruments titled "Principals' Openness and Agreeableness Questionnaire" (POAQ) and Principals' Administrative Effectiveness Questionnaire (PAEQ) which were validated by three experts were used for data collection. The questionnaires were structured on a four point scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A) Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagreed (SD) weighted 4, 3, 2 and 1. The internal consistency of the instruments was ascertained using Cronbach's Alpha and this yielded reliability coefficients of 0.81 and 0.89 POAQ and PAEQ. Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to for data analyses. P-value was used to determine the significance of the relationship.

Results

Table 1: Pearson r on the Relationship between Principals' Openness and Their Administrative Effectiveness in Secondary Schools in Anambra State

Source of Variation	n	r	P-value	Remark
Principals' Openness	263	0.88	.00	Strong Positive Relationship
Administrative Effectiveness				

The analysis in Table 1 reveals that there is a strong positive relationship of 0.88 between principals' openness and their administrative effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 2: Pearson r on the Relationship between Principals' Agreeableness and Their Administrative Effectiveness in Secondary Schools in Anambra State

Source of Variation	n	r	P-value	Remark
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Principals' Agreeableness	263	0.74	.00	Strong Positive Relationship
Administrative Effectiveness				

Table 2 reveals that there is a strong positive and significant relationship of 0.74 between principals' agreeableness and their administrative effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Discussion of Results

The findings in research question one revealed that there was a strong positive and significant correlation between principals' openness and their administrative effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State. This means that an increase in principals' openness will result to a strong increase in their administrative effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State. The openness trait of principals makes them flexible to the views and expectations of teachers. Principals who possess openness trait accept changes, eager to learn from others to increase their leadership effectiveness. This finding supports that of Khuda, Shafqat and Muhammad (2015), Danlami and Auwalu (2020), Ogbo, Oshia and Nwafor (2021) who reported that personality trait is a strong predictor of leadership effectiveness. These findings are also in conformity with the finding of Adeniyi (2014) who reported a significant relationship between openness trait and administrative effectiveness of secondary school principals.

This study also found that there is a strong positive and significant relationship of 0.74 between principals' agreeableness and their administrative effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State. Principals who possess agreeable trait are modest and avoids conflict to create conducive environment for attainment of leadership effectiveness in the school. Agreeable trait promotes principal's willing to consider teachers' opinions for stimulating their cooperation in attaining leadership effectiveness. This finding is in support of Adeniyi (2014) and Ogbo, Oshia and Nwafor (2021) that there is a significant positive relationship between agreeable trait and administrative effectiveness of secondary school principals. The finding of this study also corroborates that of Emecheta, Awa and Ukoha, (2016), Ghani, Yunus and Bahry (2016) and Sev (2019) that personality characteristics including agreeableness and openness significantly influence work performance.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that there is a strong positive and significant relationship between principals' openness and agreeableness and their leadership effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Recommendation

From the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. There is need for Post Primary School Service Commission to determine the personality traits of would be principals before their appointment to ensure that they possess the requisite traits to manage the affairs of the schools for effectiveness.
2. Post Primary School Service Commission should regularly organize professional development programmes and training for Principals geared towards developing appropriate personality traits necessary for administrative effectiveness.

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